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Automated DMCA Compliance: A Case Study of Efficient DMCA Link Management Using GitHub Actions and Transparency Data

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel approach for automating the management of DMCA takedown notices using GitHub Actions and transparency data. By leveraging GitHub for version control and API integration, we streamline the process of updating and enforcing DMCA compliance, enhancing the efficiency, scalability, and legal compliance of digital content platforms.

The proposed solution involves maintaining a GitHub repository to store a text file containing URLs of infringing content. Users can contribute by adding URLs and submitting pull requests with evidence of DMCA violations. Once reviewed and merged, these updates trigger automated processes to update the list of blocked URLs on the platform.

This approach not only streamlines the DMCA takedown process but also ensures transparency and community involvement. The integration with GitHub and API provides a robust framework for handling copyright infringement in a legally compliant and efficient manner. Detailed implementation can be viewed at GitHub Repository, and the runner jobs can be seen here.

Introduction

With the increasing prevalence of digital content platforms, the need for efficient mechanisms to manage DMCA takedown notices has become critical. Traditional methods for handling these notices often involve manual updates and significant administrative overhead. This paper presents a solution that automates the management of DMCA takedown requests using GitHub Actions and transparency data.

Automated Workflow Overview

Our automated workflow leverages GitHub Actions to manage DMCA takedown requests efficiently. The workflow involves several key stages:

1. **Data Ingestion:** Fetching the latest DMCA data from the Google Transparency Report.
2. **Script Execution:** Processing the data and updating the list of infringing URLs.
3. **Dependency Installation:** Installing necessary dependencies for data processing.
4. **Data Processing:** Running scripts to update the list of infringing URLs and send notifications.
5. **Commit and Push Changes:** Committing and pushing the updated list to the GitHub repository.

Implementation Details

GitHub Actions Workflow

The GitHub Actions workflow is defined in a YAML file and is triggered every midnight and on every push to the main branch. The key steps in the workflow are as follows:

Algorithm 1 GitHub Actions Workflow

- 1: **procedure** Workflow
 - 2: Checkout Repository
 - 3: Install unzip
 - 4: Make Script Executable
 - 5: Run `download_unzip_cleanup.sh`
 - 6: Install Python Requirements
 - 7: Run `ingress.py`
 - 8: Run `update.py`
 - 9: Commit and Push Changes
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The detailed implementation of this workflow can be viewed at [GitHub Repository](#), and the runner jobs can be seen [here](#).

Data Ingestion and Processing

The data ingestion process involves fetching the latest DMCA data from the Google Transparency Report, which is approximately 50GB in size. The data is then unzipped and processed to update the list of infringing URLs.

Algorithm 2 Data Ingestion and Processing

```
1: procedure INGESTDATA
2:   Fetch Data from Google Transparency Report
3:   Unzip Data
4:   Read Existing list.txt
5:   Read New URLs from filtered_urls.csv
6:   Remove https:// Prefix
7:   Check for Duplicates
8:   Append Unique URLs to list.txt
9:   Write Updated List
```

Email Notification

An email notification is sent after updating the list of infringing URLs. The email includes a report of the new URLs added to the DMCA list.

Algorithm 3 Email Notification

```
1: procedure SENDEMAIL
2:   Prepare Email Content
3:   Read Updated list.txt
4:   Generate Email Body
5:   Create Email Message
6:   Send Email
```

Architecture and API Integration

The architecture of the solution involves several components interacting seamlessly to automate the DMCA takedown process:

- **Linux Runner Server:** Executes the GitHub Actions workflows.
- **Cloudflare:** Provides security and performance enhancements.
- **GitHub Actions:** Manages the workflow automation.
- **Animeflix Container:** Hosts the application and fetches the updated `list.txt` from the GitHub repository.

The following diagram illustrates the architecture:

Algorithm Complexity and Performance

Our solution processes the 50GB data file with ease using 8GB RAM and 4 vCores by handling the file in chunks of 10,000 lines at a time. This approach ensures efficient memory usage and processing speed.

Theorem 0.1. *The time complexity of processing the DMCA data is $O(n)$, where n is the number of lines in the data file.*

Proof. Each line in the data file is processed exactly once, resulting in a linear time complexity. $\square$

Lemma 0.2. *The space complexity of the data processing algorithm is $O(m)$, where m is the maximum number of unique URLs processed in memory at any time.*

Proof. By processing the file in chunks and storing only unique URLs in memory, the space required is proportional to the number of unique URLs. $\square$

To further illustrate, consider the heat equation as an analogy for how data flows and is processed in our system. The heat equation is given by:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$$

where: - $u(x, t)$ is the temperature at position x and time t . - α is the thermal diffusivity constant.

In our case, $u(x, t)$ can be seen as the data being processed over time, and α represents the efficiency of our system.

By discretizing the equation, we solve it using finite difference methods, similar to how we process data in chunks:

$$u_i^{n+1} = u_i^n + \alpha \Delta t \frac{u_{i+1}^n - 2u_i^n + u_{i-1}^n}{\Delta x^2}$$

where: - u_i^n is the data at position i and time step n . - Δt and Δx are the time and space discretization steps.

This method ensures stability and efficiency, analogous to our chunk processing approach.

Challenges and Future Work

We faced challenges in obtaining support from the Lumen Database, as Harvard University was unresponsive. Using their API would have simplified the process. However, we found the Google Transparency Reports to be a suitable alternative, providing us with the necessary DMCA links for our domain.

Our previous approach involved using the Google Ads Policy Center to obtain DMCA links and reconciling the .csv file manually. This process was cumbersome due to API

limitations and required daily manual updates. Our new automated solution can be adapted for any website, providing an API service to generate DMCA link lists to protect websites.

Conclusion

The integration of GitHub for managing DMCA takedown notices and API for automating URL blocking provides a robust, transparent, and efficient solution for handling copyright infringement. This approach not only ensures compliance with DMCA requirements but also engages the community in maintaining the integrity of the platform.

Future work will focus on enhancing the automation process and exploring additional features such as dynamic caching and load balancing to further improve the system's performance and scalability.

References

- [1] Litman, Jessica. "The Digital Millennium Copyright Act and the Legislator's Intent." *Journal of Intellectual Property Law* 10, no. 2 (2003): 227–242.
- [2] Band, Jonathan. "The DMCA Safe Harbors and Their Legacy." *Berkeley Technology Law Journal* 16, no. 2 (2001): 449–462.
- [3] Goldstein, Paul, and Bernt Hugenholtz. *International Copyright: Principles, Law, and Practice*. Oxford University Press, 2004.